

Assessment of Stability Patterns in Some Selected Chilli Hybrids (*Capsicum annuum* L.)

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Authors' contributions

This work was carried out in collaboration between all authors. Author RH designed, conducted and executed the field experiment. Author TBP guided in recording the observations. Author VD conducted field level emasculation and collected floral biology of the crop. All authors read and approved the final manuscript.

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ABSTRACT

Chilli or hot pepper belongs to the family Solanaceae having diploid chromosome number of 24. It is believed to have originated from South and Central America. The genus *Capsicum* includes twenty-seven species of which five species namely *Capsicum annuum*, *C. frutescens*, *C. chinense*, *C. baccatum* and *C. pubescens* are domesticated and twenty-two undomesticated species. Hence, a field investigation carried out at three environments viz., Balajigapade - Chikkaballapur (E₁), Department of Horticulture GKVK, UAS, Bengaluru (E₂) and K- block, Department of Genetics and Plant Breeding GKVK, UAS, Bengaluru (E₃) to assess the promising hybrids for yield stability pattern and its components during *kharif* 2014-15. Twenty-five test hybrids were evaluated with three standard checks (KBCH-1, Arka Meghana and Arka Haritha) in Randomized Complete Block Design and each treatment was replicated twice. Out of three environments studied E₃ was found to be the most suitable location for expression of many bio-physical characters. Significance of variance due to hybrid X environment (linear) was evident for green fruit yield. Variance due to environment (linear) was highly significant for all the traits across three environments indicating

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considerable differences among environments and their predominant effect in the expression of all the traits. The hybrid CMS10A X Byadgi-Kaddi exhibited higher mean with unit regression coefficient and non-significant S^2_d , different from zero indicating specifically adapted to unfavorable environment for average fruit weight and fruit width. The hybrids CMS10A X LCA-206 and CMS10A X Gouribidanur were found specifically adopted to favorable environments for green fruit yield, red fruit yield, average fruits/plant and average fruit length.

Keywords: Hybrid chilli; stability; pattern; environment.

1. INTRODUCTION

Chilli or hot pepper belongs to the family Solanaceae. It is believed to have originated from South and Central America. The genus *Capsicum* includes twenty-seven species of which five species namely *Capsicum annum*, *C. frutescens*, *C. Chinense*, *C. baccatum* and *C. pubescens* are domesticated and twenty-two undomesticated species [1]. Chilli, peppers are used as green as well as dry in the form of powder and known for nutritional value, flavor, aroma, texture, color and also of medicinal value. Dry chillis are usually more pungent than the green peppers and the pungency is due to the presence of the chemical capsaicin and the bright red colour is due to the pigment capsanthin. India is the largest producer accounting for 26% of the global production followed by China [2]. Chilli is grown extensively in almost all states of the country. Karnataka is the second largest chilli growing state with an area of 0.069 Mha and production of about 0.94 m tons [3]. The yield levels of the present recommended cultivars are not satisfactory and are also not stable performers. Identification of promising hybrids with stable yields is essential to boost the average yields of chilli. To increase the present level of yield per unit area, phenotypically stable varieties are of utmost importance because the environmental conditions vary from year to year. Similarly, some varieties give high yield and suitable for particular environment and they do not perform same in other environmental conditions [4]. It is desirable to identify stable varieties even if they give fewer yields than the high yielding varieties that are unstable so as to increase the overall yield. Thus, there is a need to identify promising varieties for productivity traits. Multi environmental testing of genotypes provides an opportunity to plant breeders to identify the stability of a variety to a particular environment and also over different environments. Hence, an attempt was made to evaluate different Chilli genotypes available in Karnataka state for their yield

and yield attributes with the following objectives.

- To identify most promising hybrids for yield and its component traits.
- To assess stability pattern of selected hybrids.

2. MATERIALS AND METHODS

2.1 Experimental Design and Layout

Five lines were crossed with five testers in Line x Tester mating design to synthesize twenty-five F_1 S. The 25 crosses so synthesized and three commercial checks viz., KBCH-1, Arka Haritha and Arka Meghana were evaluated during *kharif* 2014-15 at three environments of experimental plots of Balajigapade (Chikkaballapur), Department of Horticulture, 'K' block, Department of Genetics and Plant Breeding (GPB), University of Agricultural sciences (UAS), Gandhi Krishi Vignana Kendra (GKVK), Bengaluru. The experiment was laid out in a Randomized Complete Block Design (RCBD) with two replications each genotype was grown in a single row of five-meter length consisting of 12 plants per row with a spacing of 0.40 m between plants within a row and 0.75 meter between rows. All the recommended package of practices was followed to raise a good crop.

2.2 Observations Recorded for Growth and Fruit Yield Attributes

Five representative plants in each genotype (hybrids and check) were tagged at random from each replication for recording of observations on the following traits.

1. **Green fruit yield plant⁻¹ (g):** Fresh green fruits over all pickings from five plants was weighed and expressed as grams plant⁻¹.
2. **Red fruit yield plant⁻¹ (g):** Weight of dry fruits over all pickings from other five-labeled plants was recorded and expressed as grams plant⁻¹.

3. **Fruits plant⁻¹**: Total number of green fruits over all pickings were counted and expressed on per plant basis.
4. **Average fruit length (cm)**: The length of ten fruits were measured from the tip to the base excluding the pedicel and expressed as a mean of ten fruits in centimeters.
5. **Average fruit weight (g)**: The weight of 10 randomly chosen fruits were recorded in grams and expressed as the mean.
6. **Fruit width (cm)**: The ten fruits chosen for estimating fruit length were measured at their maximum width and expressed as centimeters per fruit.

Table 1. List of test hybrids and check hybrids used for experiment

Sl. No	Hybrids
1	CMS6A X Gouribidanur
2	CMS 6A X Tiwari
3	CMS 6A X Byadgi kaddi
4	CMS 6A X Byadgi dabbi
5	CMS 6A X LCA 206
6	CMS 7A X Gouribidanur
7	CMS 7A X Tiwari
8	CMS 7A X Byadgi kaddi
9	CMS 7A X Byadgi dabbi
10	CMS 7A X LCA 206
11	CMS 8A X Gouribidanur
12	CMS 8A X Tiwari
13	CMS 8A X Byadgi kaddi
14	CMS 8A X Byadgi dabbi
15	CMS 8A X LCA 206
16	CMS 9A X Gouribidanur
17	CMS 9A X Tiwari
18	CMS 9A X Byadgi kaddi
19	CMS 9A X Byadgi dabbi
20	CMS 9A X LCA 206
21	CMS 10A X Gouribidanur
22	CMS 10A X Tiwari
23	CMS 10A X Byadgi kaddi
24	CMS 10A X Byadgi dabbi
25	CMS 10A X LCA 206
26	KBCH-1
27	Arka Haritha
28	Arka Meghana

2.3 Statistical Analysis

The estimate of deviations from regression (S^2_{di}) suggests the degree of reliance that should be placed on the linear regression in interpretation of the results. If these values are significantly deviating from zero, the expected phenotype cannot be predicted satisfactorily. When, deviations (S^2_{di}) are not significant the conclusion may be drawn by the joint consideration of mean, yield and regression coefficient (b_i) values (Finlay and Wilkinson, [5]; Eberhart and Russell, [6]) as below.

Stable genotypes: A hybrid with unit regression co-efficient ($b_i=1$) and the deviation not significantly different from zero ($S^2_{di} = 0$) was considered widely adaptable.

Regression coefficient	Stability	Mean yield	Remarks
$b = 1$	Average	High	Well adopted to all environments
$b = 0$	Average	Low	Poorly adopted to all environments
$b > 1$	Below average	High	Specifically adapted to favorable environments
$b < 1$	Above average	High	Specifically adapted to unfavorable environments

3. RESULTS

3.1 Analysis of Variance

Analysis of variance indicated mean sum of squares for hybrids were highly significant for the expression of all the productive traits (Table 2) indicating the presence of variability among the hybrids. Variance due to environments was highly significant for all the productive traits across three environments. High proportion of variation on yield was for the environment effect, therefore more testing sites are needed or the environments in locations need to be controlled. Variance due to environment (linear) was highly significant for all the productive traits across three environments. The additive environmental variance was found to be considerable magnitude. Variance due to pooled deviation was significant for all the productive traits across three environments thus indicating that the unpredictable partition formed the major part of G x E interaction that the genotypes tested differed considerably in their stability for the characters.

The estimates of stability parameters viz., mean (μ_j), regression (b_i) and deviation from regression (S^2_{di}) as presented in Table 2.

3.2 Green Fruit Yield Plant⁻¹

Stability pattern for green fruit yield are summarized Table 3a Among the 28 hybrids, the test hybrids CMS 6A x LCA 206, CMS 7A x LCA 206, CMS 8A x Tiwari, CMS 8A x Tiwari, CMS 9A x LCA 206, Arka Haritha and Arka Meghana recorded lower mean than the overall mean and these hybrids showed regression co-efficient being equal to unity ($b_i = 1$). The test

hybrids CMS 10A x LCA 206, CMS 8A x LCA 206, CMS 8A x LCA 206, CMS 10A x LCA 206 and KBCH-1 recorded higher mean than the overall mean and these hybrids showed regression co-efficient being more than the unity ($b_i > 1$). The test hybrids CMS 10A x Gouribidanur, CMS 6A x Tiwari, CMS 7A x Tiwari, CMS 6A x Gouribidanur, CMS 6A x Byadgi kaddi, CMS 7A x Byadgi kaddi and CMS 9A x Byadgi kaddi recorded higher mean than the overall mean and these hybrids showed regression co-efficient being lower than the unity ($b_i < 1$).

3.3 Red Fruit Yield Plant⁻¹

Stability pattern for red fruit yield are summarized Table 3b. Among 28 hybrids, the test hybrids CMS 6A x Tiwari, CMS 6A x Byadgi kaddi, CMS 7A x Tiwari, CMS 7A x Byadgi dabbi, CMS 7A x LCA 206, CMS 8A x Gouribidanur, CMS 8A x Tiwari, CMS 8A x Byadgi dabbi, CMS 8A x LCA 206, CMS 9A x Tiwari, CMS 9A x Byadgi kaddi, CMS 9A x Byadgi dabbi, CMS 9A x LCA 206 and CMS 10A x Byadgi dabbi recorded lower mean than the overall mean and these hybrids showed regression co-efficient being equal to unity ($b_i = 1$). The test hybrids CMS 6A x Gouribidanur, CMS 7A x Byadgi kaddi, CMS 8A x Byadgi kaddi, CMS 10A x Byadgi kaddi and CMS 10A x LCA 206 recorded higher mean than the overall mean and these hybrids showed regression co-efficient being more than the unity ($b_i > 1$). The test hybrids CMS 6A x LCA 206, CMS 7A x Gouribidanur, CMS 10A x Gouribidanur, CMS 10A x Tiwari KBCH-1 and Arka Meghana recorded higher mean than the overall mean and these hybrids showed regression co-efficient being lower than the unity ($b_i < 1$). Among the different hybrids studied, 14 hybrids recorded lower mean than the overall mean and these hybrids showed regression co-efficient being equal to unity ($b_i = 1$) there by indicating average stability and suggesting suitability for well adaptability to all environments, six hybrids recorded higher mean than the overall mean and these hybrids showed regression co-efficient being lower than the unity ($b_i < 1$) there by indicating above average stability and suggesting suitability for specifically adapted to unfavourable environments as suggested by Finlay and Wilkinson, [5]; Eberhart and Russell, [6].

3.4 Average Fruits Plant⁻¹

Stability pattern for Average fruits per plant are summarized Table 3c. Among the 28 hybrids, the

test hybrids CMS 6A x LCA 206, CMS 8A x Byadgi kaddi, CMS 9A x Gouribidanur, CMS 9A x Byadgi kaddi, Arka Haritha and Arka Meghana recorded lower mean than the overall mean and these hybrids showed regression co-efficient being equal to unity ($b_i = 1$). The test hybrids CMS 7A x Gouribidanur, CMS 7A x Tiwari, CMS 8A x Gouribidanur, CMS 8A x LCA 206, CMS 7A x Byadgi dabbi, CMS 8A x Byadgi dabbi, CMS 7A x LCA 206, CMS 10A x Tiwari and CMS 10A x LCA 206 recorded higher mean than the overall mean and these hybrids showed regression co-efficient being more than the unity ($b_i > 1$). The test hybrids CMS 6A x Gouribidanur, CMS 7A x Byadgi kaddi, CMS 10A x Gouribidanur and KBCH-1 recorded higher mean than the overall mean and these hybrids showed regression co-efficient being lower than the unity ($b_i < 1$). Six out of 28 hybrids recorded lower mean than the overall mean and these hybrids showed regression co-efficient being equal to unity ($b_i = 1$) there by indicating average stability and suggesting suitability for well adaptability to all environments, four hybrids recorded higher mean than the overall mean and these hybrids showed regression co-efficient being lower than the unity ($b_i < 1$) there by indicating above average stability and suggesting suitability for specifically adapted to unfavourable environments as suggested by Finlay and Wilkinson, [5]; Eberhart and Russell, [6].

3.5 Average Fruit Length (cm)

Stability pattern for Average fruits per plant are summarized in Table 3d. Among the 28 hybrids, the test hybrids CMS 6A x Gouribidanur, CMS 6A x Tiwari, CMS 7A x Gouribidanur, CMS 7A x Tiwari, CMS 8A x Gouribidanur, CMS 9A x Tiwari, KBCH-1, Arka Haritha and Arka Meghana recorded lower mean than the overall mean and these hybrids showed regression co-efficient being equal to unity ($b_i = 1$). The test hybrids CMS 7A x LCA 206, CMS 8A x LCA 206 and CMS 10A x LCA 206 recorded higher mean than the overall mean and these hybrids showed regression co-efficient being more than the unity ($b_i > 1$). The test hybrids CMS 6A x Byadgi dabbi, CMS 6A x Byadgi kaddi, CMS 7A x Byadgi kaddi, CMS 7A x Byadgi dabbi, CMS 8A x Byadgi dabbi, CMS 9A x Byadgi kaddi, CMS 9A x Byadgi dabbi and CMS 10A x Byadgi dabbi recorded higher mean than the overall mean and these hybrids showed regression co-efficient being lower than the unity ($b_i < 1$). Eight hybrids recorded higher mean than

Table 2. ANOVA for fruit yield and its component traits

Source of variance	df	Green fruit yield plant ⁻¹ (g)	Red fruit yield plant ⁻¹ (g)	Fruits plant ⁻¹	Average fruit length (cm)	Average fruit weight (g)	Average fruit width (cm)
Rep within environment	3	8031.33	59.58	774.30	0.02	0.24	0.008
Hybrids	27	30430.24**	1611.30*	2463.41 **	10.35**	3.46**	0.06**
Environment + (Hybrids x Environment)	56	15450.02	1222.39	711.52	0.86	0.13	0.01**
Environments	2	43692.14*	9656.72**	3635.90 **	4.82**	1.05**	0.19**
Hybrids x Environment	54	14404.01	910.01	603.21	0.71	0.10	0.003
Environments (Lin.)	1	87384.30**	19313.44**	7271.78**	9.65**	2.11 **	0.39**
Hybrids x Environment (Lin.)	27	19646.98*	936.94	768.27	0.66	0.03	0.002
Pooled Deviation	28	8833.87**	851.53**	422.50**	0.74***	0.16**	0.003
Pooled Error	81	770.34	48.74	66.13	0.046	0.01	0.003

* Significant @P = 0.05 and ** Significant @P = 0.01

Fig. 1. Relationship between regression coefficient (b_i) and S^2d_i for green fruit yield plant⁻¹

Fig. 2. Relationship between regression coefficient (b_i) and S^2d_i for red fruit yield plant⁻¹

Fig. 3. Relationship between regression coefficient (b_i) and S^2d_i for number of fruits plant⁻¹

Fig. 4. Relationship between regression coefficient (b_i) and S^2d_i for average fruit length

Fig. 5. Relationship between regression coefficient (b_i) and S^2d_i for average fruit weight

the overall mean and these hybrids showed regression co-efficient being lower than the unity ($b_i < 1$) there by indicating above average stability and suggesting suitability for specifically adapted to unfavourable environments as suggested by Finlay and Wilkinson, [5]; Eberhart and Russell, [6].

3.6 Average Fruit Weight (g)

Stability pattern for Average fruits per plant are summarized Table 3e. Among the 28 hybrids, the test hybrid CMS 6A x Tiwari recorded higher mean than the overall mean and these hybrids showed regression co-efficient being equal to the unity ($b_i = 1$). The test hybrids CMS 7A x Gouribidanur, CMS 7A x Tiwari, CMS 7A x Byadagi dabbi, CMS 9A x LCA 206, CMS 10A

x Byadagi dabbi, CMS 10A x LCA 206 and Arka Haritha recorded lower mean than the overall mean and these hybrids showed regression co-efficient being equal to unity ($b_i = 1$). The test hybrids CMS 6A x Gouribidanur, CMS 6A x Byadagi kaddi, CMS 6A x Byadagi dabbi, CMS 7A x LCA 206, CMS 8A x Byadagi dabbi, CMS 8A x Byadagi kaddi, CMS 9A x Gouribidanur, CMS 9A x Byadagi dabbi and CMS 9A x Byadagi kaddi recorded higher mean than the overall mean and these hybrids showed regression co-efficient being more than the unity ($b_i > 1$). The test hybrids CMS 7A x Byadagi kaddi, CMS 8A x Byadagi kaddi and Arka Meghana recorded higher mean than the overall mean and these hybrids showed regression co-efficient being lower than the unity ($b_i < 1$). CMS 6A x Tiwari recorded higher mean than the

Fig. 6. Relationship between regression coefficient (b_i) and S^2d_i for fruit width

Table 3a. Pattern of stability for green fruit yield per plant in chilli

Sl. No.	Pattern	Mean regression	Crosses
1	Average	High ($b=1$)	
2	Average	Low ($b=1$)	CMS 6A x LCA 206 CMS 7A x LCA 206 CMS 8A x Tiwari CMS 9A x Gouribidanur CMS 9A x LCA 206 Arka Haritha Arka Meghana
3	Below average	High ($b > 1$)	CMS 8A x Gouribidanur CMS 8A x LCA 206 CMS 10A x Tiwari CMS 10A x LCA 206 KBCH-1
4	Above average	High ($b < 1$)	CMS 6A x Tiwari CMS 6A x Gouribidanur CMS 6A x Byadgi kaddi CMS 7A x Byadgi kaddi CMS 9A x Byadgi kaddi CMS 10A x Gouribidanur

Table 3b. Pattern of stability for red fruit yield per plant in chilli

Sl. No.	Pattern	Mean regression	Crosses
1	Average	High (b=1)	
2	Average	Low (b=1)	CMS 6A x Tiwari CMS 6A x Byadgi kaddi CMS 7A x Tiwari CMS 7A x Byadgi dabbi CMS 7A x LCA 206 CMS 8A x Gouribidanur CMS 8A x Tiwari CMS 8A x Byadagi dabbi CMS 8A x LCA 206 CMS 9A x Tiwari CMS 9A x Byadagi kaddi CMS 9A x Byadagi dabbi CMS 9A x LCA 206 CMS 10A x Byadagi dabbi
3	Below average	High (b>1)	CMS 6A x Gouribidanur CMS 7A x Byadgi kaddi CMS 8A x Byadgi kaddi CMS 10A x Byadgi kaddi CMS 10A x LCA 206
4	Above average	High (b <1)	CMS6A x LCA 206 CMS 7A x Gouribidanur CMS 10A x Gouribidanur CMS 10A x Tiwari Arka Meghana

Table 3c. Pattern of stability for average fruits per plant in chilli

Sl. No.	Pattern	Mean regression	Crosses
1	Average	High (b=1)	
2	Average	Low (b=1)	CMS 6A x LCA 206 CMS 6A x Byadagi kaddi CMS 6A x Tiwari CMS 7A x LCA 206 CMS 8A x Byadgi kaddi CMS 8A x Tiwari CMS 9A x Gouribidanur CMS 9A x Byadagi kaddi CMS 10A x Byadagi kaddi Arka Haritha Arka Meghana
3	Below average	High (b>1)	CMS 7A x Gouribidanur CMS 7A x Tiwari CMS 8A x Gouribidanur CMS 8A x LCA 206 CMS 7A x Byadgi dabbi CMS 7A x LCA 206 CMS 8A x Byadgi dabbi CMS 10A x Tiwari CMS 10A x LCA 206
4	Above average	High (b <1)	CMS 6A x Gouribidanur CMS 7A x Byadagi kaddi CMS 10A x Gouribidanur KBCH-1

overall mean and this hybrid showed regression co-efficient being equal to the unity ($b_i = 1$) there by indicating average stability and suggesting suitability for well adopted to all environments. Eight hybrids recorded lower mean than the overall mean and these hybrids showed regression co-efficient being equal to unity ($b_i = 1$) there by indicating average stability and suggesting suitability for well adaptability to all environments, three hybrids recorded higher mean than the overall mean and these hybrids showed regression co-efficient being lower than the unity ($b_i < 1$) there by indicating above average stability and suggesting suitability for specifically adapted to unfavourable environments as suggested by Finlay and Wilkinson, [5]; Eberhart and Russell, [6].

3.7 Fruit Width (cm)

Stability pattern for Average fruits per plant are summarized Table 3f. Among the 28 hybrids the test hybrid CMS 9A x LCA 206 recorded higher mean than the overall mean and these hybrids showed regression co-efficient being equal to the unity ($b_i = 1$). The test hybrids CMS 6A x Byadagi dabbi, CMS 7A x Gouribidanur, CMS 7A x Byadagi dabbi, CMS 7A x LCA 206, CMS 8A x LCA 206, CMS 8A x Byadagi dabbi, CMS 9A x Byadagi dabbi, CMS 10A x Gouribidanur, CMS 10A x LCA 206, CMS 10A x Tiwari, KBCH -1 and Arka Meghana recorded lower mean than the overall mean and these hybrids showed

regression co-efficient being equal to unity ($b_i = 1$). The test hybrids CMS 6A x Gouribidanur, CMS 6A x Tiwari, CMS 6A x Byadagi kaddi, CMS 7A x Byadagi kaddi, CMS 8A x Byadagi kaddi, CMS 9A x Gouribidanur, CMS 7A x LCA 206, CMS 8A x Byadagi dabbi, CMS 9A x Tiwari, CMS 9A x Byadagi kaddi and CMS 10A x Byadagi kaddi recorded higher mean than the overall mean and these hybrids showed regression co-efficient being more than the unity ($b_i > 1$). The test hybrids CMS 8A x Gouribidanur, CMS 8A x Tiwari and Arka Meghana recorded higher mean than the overall mean and these hybrids showed regression co-efficient being lower than the unity ($b_i < 1$). CMS 9A x LCA 206 recorded higher mean than the overall mean and this hybrid showed regression co-efficient being equal to the unity ($b_i = 1$) their by indicating average stability and suggesting suitability for well adopted to all environments. 12 hybrids recorded lower mean than the overall mean and these hybrids showed regression co-efficient being equal to unity ($b_i = 1$) there by indicating average stability and suggesting suitability for well adaptability to all environments, three hybrids recorded higher mean than the overall mean and these hybrids showed regression co-efficient being lower than the unity ($b_i < 1$) there by indicating above average stability and suggesting suitability for specifically adapted to unfavourable environments as suggested by Finlay and Wilkinson [5]; Eberhart and Russell, [6].

Table 3d. Pattern of stability for average fruit length in chilli

Sl. No.	Pattern	Mean regression	Crosses
1	Average	High ($b=1$)	
2	Average	Low ($b=1$)	CMS 6A x Gouribidanur CMS 7A x Gouribidanur CMS 7A x Tiwari CMS 6A x Tiwari CMS 8A x Gouribidanur CMS 9A x Tiwari KBCH-1 Arka Haritha Arka Meghana
3	Below average	High ($b>1$)	CMS 7A x LCA 206 CMS 8A x LCA 206 CMS 10A x LCA 206
4	Above average	High ($b < 1$)	CMS 6A x Byadagi dabbi CMS 6A x Byadagi kaddi CMS 7A x Byadagi kaddi CMS 7A x Byadagi dabbi CMS 9A x Byadagi kaddi CMS 9A x Byadagi dabbi CMS 6A x Byadagi dabbi

Table 3e. Pattern of stability for average fruit weight in chilli

Sl. No.	Pattern	Mean regression	Crosses
1	Average	High (b=1)	CMS 6A x Tiwari
2	Average	Low (b=1)	CMS 7A x Gouribidanur CMS 7A x Tiwari CMS 7A x Byadagi dabbi CMS 9A x LCA 206 CMS 10A x Byadagi dabbi CMS 10A x LCA 206 Arka Haritha
3	Below average	High (b>1)	CMS 6A x Gouribidanur CMS 6A x Byadagi kaddi CMS 6A x Byadagi dabbi CMS 8A x Byadagi dabbi CMS 8A x Byadagi kaddi CMS 9A x Gouribidanur CMS 9A x Byadagi dabbi CMS 9A x Byadagi kaddi
4	Above average	High (b <1)	CMS 7A x Byadagi kaddi CMS 8A x Byadagi kaddi Arka Meghana

Table 3f. Pattern of stability for fruit width in chilli

Sl No.	Pattern	Mean regression	Crosses
1	Average	High (b=1)	CMS 9A x LCA 206
2	Average	Low (b=1)	CMS 6A x Gouribidanur CMS 7A x Byadagi dabbi CMS 6A x Byadagi dabbi CMS 8A x LCA 206 CMS 8A x Byadagi dabbi CMS 9A x Byadagi dabbi CMS 10A x Byadagi dabbi CMS 10A x LCA 206 CMS 10A x Tiwari Arka Haritha KBCH -1
3	Below average	High (b>1)	CMS 6A x Gouribidanur CMS 6A x Tiwari CMS 6A x Byadagi kaddi CMS 7A x Byadagi kaddi CMS 8A x Byadagi kaddi CMS 9A x Gouribidanur CMS 9A x Tiwari CMS 9A x Byadagi kaddi
4	Above average	High (b <1)	CMS 10A x Byadagi kaddi CMS 8A x gouribidanur CMS 8A x Tiwari Arka Meghana

4. CONCLUSION

The test hybrid CMS10A x Byadgi Kaddi exhibited higher mean with unit regression coefficient (b_i>1) and the deviation non-significantly

different from zero ($S^2_{di} = 0$) indicated that it is specifically adapted to favourable environment for the productive traits viz., average fruit weight (gm) and fruit width (cm). The hybrid CMS10A x Gouribidanur for green fruit yield plant⁻¹,

CMS10A × LCA 206 for red fruit yield plant⁻¹ and CMS8A × Byadgi Dabbi for number of fruits exhibited high mean with unit regression coefficient ($b_i > 1$) and the deviation non-significantly different from zero ($S^2_{di} = 0$) indicated below average stability specifically adapted to favourable locations for the productive traits. The test Hybrids CMS 6A × Tiwari for the character average fruit weight and CMS 9A × LCA 206 for the character fruit width. These hybrids found well adopted to all environments. The test hybrid CMS 10A × Gouribidanur was found specifically adopted to favourable environments for the productive traits green fruit yield, red fruit yield and average fruits per plant. The present investigation revealed that the test hybrid CMS10A × Gouribidanur was found promising and highly adaptable different across different environments.

COMPETING INTERESTS

Authors have declared that no competing interests exist.

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